

PRIORITY AREAS FOR DIVERSIFICATION AND SEASONALITY OF THE TOURISM PRODUCT

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ABSTRACT

Seasonality provokes downtime of accommodation facilities and temporary unemployment of staff. The purpose of the study is to identify potential opportunities to smooth out the impact of seasonality on the tourism industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Statistical data analysis, induction and deduction were used to identify influence. An analysis of the literature on tourism research by authors from Russia, Uzbekistan and other countries was carried out. In addition, the characteristics of the seasonality factor in tourism require more detailed consideration. The article examines the importance of seasonality in the activation of tourism services in the socio-economic development of the country, the impact on the development of the tourism industry. The developed measures to smooth out the influence of seasonality can be applied not only in Uzbekistan, but also in other countries with similar characteristics of the tourism industry.

Keywords: tourism branch of the region; tourism branch; region; the influence of seasonality; seasonality; additive seasonality; a number of arrived tourists; smoothing of seasonality impact; Uzbekistan; Surkhandarya region; tourism policy.

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is the most rapidly developing low-cost, high-income sector of the world economy, second only to oil and gas, and the automobile industry. Over the past fifty years, it has become the main means of global development, contributing to the social and economic recovery of human life, an important sector of the economy taking into account the multiplier effect in the relevant sectors, its share in the world GDP provides 6%, 6-7% of employment, and 30% of service exports^{1,1}

¹ <https://www.unwto.org>¹

The development of tourism stimulates the development of other economy branches since this area requires a wide infrastructure (communications, roads, public services, catering establishments, amusement parks). Significant fluctuations in the performance of the tourism industry due to seasonality hinder its development. Seasonality provokes downtime, the insufficient workload of accommodation facilities, as well as temporary unemployment of personnel in the tourism sector. Therefore, the study of seasonality as a factor in the development of the tourism branch is relevant and has priority.

For Uzbekistan, smoothing seasonality will lead to accelerated development of the tourism industry, which, as a result of the multiplier effect, stimulates the growth of the whole national economy.

This does not mean that 80% of people arrived to visit their relatives and friends do not have a holiday in Uzbekistan. Rather, it characterizes the tourists who arrived in Uzbekistan as supporters of budget holidays. Such tourists have priority in saving from staying with family and friends instead of staying at a hostel or hotel. Demand for budget types of recreation in Uzbekistan is also one of the features of the tourism industry.

One of the directions of tourism promotion in Uzbekistan is ecotourism. There was open access to a number of artificial lakes and reservoirs for such tourism development and further diversification of tourism products. The first stage provides the organization of ecotourism on the territory of 18 reservoirs, which are located in the following areas: Andijan, Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Namangan, Samarkand, Surkhandarya, Tashkent and Ferghana.

Most often, seasonality research in tourism is devoted either to the seasonality of certain types of tourism or to forecasting the performance of a tourism company or industry (the volume of services sold, profit, occupancy of rooms).

As a feature of the study of the tourism industry seasonality in Uzbekistan, it should be noted that seasonality is only mentioned as one of the factors of the tourism industry development.

Thus, the novelty of the study lies in the analysis of the seasonality of tourism as an object of study and the use of actual values of the number of tourists entering as initial data.

To achieve this goal it is necessary to solve several problems. First of all, it is necessary to analyze the literature regarding researches of tourism in general and seasonality in the tourism industry by authors from Russia, Uzbekistan, CIS and other countries. Analysis of the seasonality impact on the tourism industry in the region is an integral part of the analysis of the seasonality impact on tourism development in the

whole country. Therefore, it is necessary to study seasonality in Uzbekistan, and only then to study the effect of seasonality on the tourism industry in the region. Based on the analysis, it is necessary to identify potential opportunities to smooth out the impact of seasonality on the tourism industry in the region.

The scientific novelty of the study is the identification of universal main sources and directions for smoothing the seasonality influence on the tourism industry of the regions.

Potentially developed measures can be applied not only in Uzbekistan but also in other countries with similar climatic characteristics.

The theoretical and practical significance of the scientific results obtained in the study is determined by the relevance of the problem and the knowledge of the topic. The provisions and conclusions formulated in the work contribute to the development of ideas about the degree of seasonality influence on indicators of the tourism industry. Practical recommendations can be applied in the development of government policies and measures aimed at smoothing the impact of seasonality on the indicators of the tourism industry.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As part of the study, it is necessary to provide definitions of the following terms.

Seasonality is a steady (from year to year) recurring, cyclical tourism activity of a location, associated with a change in recreation conditions (Durovich, A.P. and Kopanev, A.S. 1998). As for the tourism branch, seasonality is expressed in the alternation of peaks and falls in demand for tourism services.

As for assessing the results of tourism development in the territory, there are obvious direct indicators of activity. These indicators include the total income of tourism enterprises (travel agents, tour operators, tour agencies) and enterprises representing accommodation facilities (hostels, hotels, motels, etc.). In this case, the income of enterprises related to the infrastructure of the territory (leisure centres, catering and transport enterprises) is not taken into account.

Another drawback is the lack of separation of export and import services. For example, the income of a tour operator selling tours abroad will be taken into account as a result of the tourism industry. However, they will not contribute to tourism development in the territory with such an operator. In this regard, the most suitable and objective data for the analysis of the seasonality of the tourism industry are data on the number of tourists arriving.

There were used such methods as analysis and synthesis of statistical data, description, comparison, induction and deduction. These methods help to determine the degree of seasonality influence on the tourism industry of the country as a whole

and the region in particular. Identification of potential opportunities to smooth out the impact of seasonality on the tourism industry in the region is inextricably linked to the analysis of statistical data. The use of comparative analysis, induction and deduction is necessary to obtain correct and reasonable research results.

The method of induction in the study was used to identify potential opportunities to smooth the impact of seasonality on the tourism industry using a specific region as an example and extending them to regions with similar characteristics. Thus, according to the results of the study, universal main sources and directions of smoothing out the influence of seasonality on the tourism industry of the regions were identified.

LITERATURE REVIEW

World authors' researches of the tourism industry

One of the most advanced researches of tourism is the study of climate change, populations and animal migration pathways that have a direct impact on tourism (Lipka, 2018; Setyawan et al. 2018). In light of the growing popularity of tourism types associated with the observation of animals and the study of the animal world, these studies are of particular relevance.

Studies of authors from other countries concern the impact of the tourism industry on the development of related industries, the creation of new jobs, and, as a result, the promotion of territorial development (Buletova et al., 2015; Pei Ti and Turgut, 2010). The analysis of the impact of tourism development on small and medium-sized businesses (Battistella et al., 2018), improve of the life quality of the local population (Ibanescu, B.C. et al. 2018) and economic growth (Ozturk, 2016) is of particular importance. An analysis of certain types of tourism industry revenues is also important, for example, recreational vacation fees (Tsung-Chiung, 2010). Therefore, to assess the socio-economic results of the development of the tourism industry in a particular territory, the use of complex indicators is necessary (Scharl et al., 2003).

A comprehensive impact of the development of the tourism industry on various aspects of the functioning of the country's economy is evident from the questions above.

The general methodological approach to tourism management in the region includes approaches to the various stages of the strategic development of the destination, cluster and tourist area (Wang et al., 2010; Wöber, 2003; Wolk and Wöber, 2008). In the case of a formal approach to tourism management in the region, it will not be possible to achieve growth in tourism income in the long term.

State targeted programs are used to stimulate the development of the tourism industry (Songshan, 2010). These programs, in particular, include a number of activities aimed at improving competitiveness (Mazanec et al., 2007; Popescu et al.,

2018). Performance indicators for the performance of these programs and their effectiveness are also the subject of research by foreign authors (Rodella et al., 2017). State programs to support and stimulate the development of the tourism industry are an effective method of promoting tourism.

To ensure the completeness of the study of the tourism industry, it is necessary to analyze not only at the macro-level, as presented above, but also at the micro-level. Thus, the organization's leadership and the goals it sets for the enterprise have a significant impact on tourism development (Solveig and Gro, 2012).

Analysis of seasonality as a factor in the development of the tourism industry is also an urgent research topic and was carried out by many authors (Rantala et al., 2019; Fabbri, 2012; Weiermair et al., 2006; Baum and Lundtorp, 2001). Thus, foreign authors attach great importance to seasonality as a factor in the development of the tourism industry.

Tourism researches of authors from Russia, Uzbekistan and other CIS countries

The development of the tourism industry has a direct and indirect impact on the development of related industries and the national economy on the whole (Dekhtyaruk et al., 2014). The first reason is that tourism development requires a wide infrastructure.

One of the most relevant areas of tourism research is the analysis of clusters, destinations and the tourism industry of the region (Kamalova et al., 2017; Kolyadin, 2018; Tokhirov, 2017; Khamidova, 2017; Khidirova, 2017; Hodachek and Shamakhov, 2017; Stepanova, 2016; Kulibanova and Teor, 2017). It is the development of tourist facilities (tourist areas, clusters or destinations) that is the basis for the development of the tourism industry in the region.

Lack of attention to the development and formation of tourist zones of the territory leads to the fact that only individual investment projects are fully operational. For this reason, in the long-term, there is no stable growth in tourism revenue and territory attendance (Aleksandrova, 2015).

Regional Programs and Strategies for tourism territories development are effective methods for promoting the tourism industry (Tohirov, 2017; Khashimov and Kim, 2014). Indicators for evaluating the performance of these programs and their effectiveness are also studied (Vershina and Orlova, 2019).

A full production cycle in the tourism branch is possible if administrative and market relations are established on the territory. Then the main tourist flow and the activities of infrastructure enterprises (leisure centres, catering and transport enterprises, etc.) located in the nearby territory will be ensured (Alexandrova, 2015). Thus, the developed infrastructure promotes and accelerates the promotion of tourism.

And a low level of infrastructure development will be a significant obstacle to the growth of the tourism industry.

Social media analysis is a growing area in recreational geography. The interest is associated with statistical data that are difficult to obtain when conducting studies by classical methods (Tikunov et al., 2018). New non-standard methods of obtaining statistics on tourism are becoming increasingly relevant.

The analysis of seasonality as a factor in the development of the tourism industry is also an urgent research topic and was carried out by many authors (Otto and Redkin, 2015; Rakhimov and Kurbanova, 2012; Khamzaeva, 2019; Khashimov and Kim, 2014). Thus, both foreign and domestic authors attach great importance to seasonality as a factor in the development of the tourism industry.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The conditions of seasonalization of tourist products and its assessment are important scientific-practical and methodological aspects of the development of the tourism industry. Seasonality in tourism is determined by a number of conditions:

- natural climate - quantitative and qualitative indicators, sports, health, education and other types of tourism;
- economic - composition of consumption of goods and services, formation of demand's solvency through supply;
- social - availability of free time;
- demographic - demand differentiated by age structure and other characteristics;
- psychological - traditions, fashion, imitation;
- material and technical - accommodation, transport, cultural services.
- technological - comprehensive approach to providing quality services.

The tourist product is produced by two subjects of the market - the tourist region (its management system, enterprises and organizations that produce services and works that satisfy tourist needs) and the tour operator. The tourist product in the region is formed taking into account the market conditions or a certain order of the tourist. The development evolution of the tourist product in the market is characterized by the concept of its life cycle. It consists in dividing the market life cycle of a tourist product into market entry, growth, maturity, saturation, and decline stages characterized by changes in sales volume, costs, profit, and other indicators.

From 2016 to 2019, there was a steady increase in the number of companies and organizations that carried out tourist activities, the total number of people provided services, and the value of sold tourist tickets, while the remaining indicators showed negative trends. In particular, compared to 2016, in 2019, the total number of services provided increased by 102%, the number of one-day visitors increased by 166%, the

number of overnight visitors increased by 38%, and the number of tourist tickets sold increased by 43%, as a result of which we can see that the income from referrals is 787,386 million soms and has increased considerably. But in 2020, due to the quarantine measures introduced due to the global pandemic, there was a decrease in all indicators, including the number of companies and organizations that carried out total tourism activities in 2020 by 41%, the number of visitors served by 156%, the number of sold tourism compared to 2019 that the number of passes has decreased by 67%, directly as a result of this, the income from the sold tourist passes has sharply decreased and amounted to 143.372 million soms. As a result of the easing of quarantine rules by 2021 and the opportunities created for the development of the tourism sector, growth trends have been achieved in 2022 compared to 2020. If we pay attention to the changes in 2022 compared to 2021, it can be seen that in 2022 the number of companies and organizations that implemented tourism activities increased by 21%, the number of visitors served increased by 17%, but we see that the number of tourist tickets has decreased by 35%. Nevertheless, the value of tourist passes sold in 2022 was 519,234 million soms, which was a 49% increase compared to 2020.

If we analyze the travel goals of foreign citizens who came to the Republic of Uzbekistan for tourist purposes based on the data, in 2012-2016, those who came to see relatives and friends accounted for an average of 80.8 percent, and in 2017-2018 the percentage of visitors to the destination increased to 84-88%, although it decreased to 80% in 2019, we can see that this indicator has increased again in the last 2 years and has been a significant amount around 87-89% until now. . If we pay attention, those who came to study for 10 years made an average of 0.3 percent. Other reasons, including those who came for treatment, on the contrary, averaged 4.5 percent in 2012-2014, and decreased sharply in the following years, 1 percent in 2017, 0.9 percent in 2019, gradually in 2021. the increase was 1.7 percent. 1.3% in 2021 and 2022. The dynamics of foreigners who came to provide services and attend business meetings was the same, that is, there was an increase in 2012-2016, and a decrease in 2017-2020. In 2012-2018, the number of people who came for tourism and recreation was on average 8.5%, in 2019 this figure increased sharply and reached 15.4%, by 2020 it will rise to 8.5% due to the pandemic and again in 2021 grew up. In 2022, it will be 7.5 percent, while the downward trend is observed. This situation is one of the unique features of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan. Thus, very few tourists consider Uzbekistan only as a place of rest. But this does not mean that 85-89 percent of those who come to visit their relatives and friends do not rest in the territory of Uzbekistan. Rather, it characterizes tourists who come to Uzbekistan as supporters of budget vacations.

The third paragraph of this chapter is entitled “The main trends in the seasonality of tourism products”. It contains the monthly index of foreign tourists who visited Uzbekistan in 2018-2022, and the number of foreign tourists who visited Uzbekistan from the CIS and foreign countries in 2018-2021 by month.

As part of the research, a linear trend for 2018-2022 was created based on the data on the number of tourists who came to the Republic of Uzbekistan in the months of 2018-2022. As can be seen from the above graphic data, a steady growth trend of the number of tourists arriving in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2018-2019 is observed. This trend indicates that there is a significant potential for the development of tourism in Uzbekistan. But in the last months of 2019 and in 2020, the number of arrivals to our country decreased sharply due to the reasons of COVID-19, and only due to the work carried out in 2021, we can observe an increase in the number of arrivals in 2021-2022. Additive seasonality by month is calculated as the average deviation of the number of tourists from a linear trend for each month using Microsoft Excel. The additive seasonality table shows significant changes in the number of tourists entering the Republic of Uzbekistan throughout the year. Deviations for the year reach 40% of the average value. The results of the assessment of the seasonality factor show that the non-seasonal months, that is, the months with the lowest number of incoming tourists are January, February, April and December in the first, second, fourth and last months of the year, and the highest number of tourists And some of them visit in August, September and October.

CONCLUSION

Several conclusions can be drawn as a result of the scientific research carried out within the framework of the dissertation research. The most important of them are:

1. The competitiveness of tourism firms in the market depends on the satisfaction of customers' needs, as well as the financial results of their activities, on a correctly chosen diversification strategy for tourism companies. Therefore, the conditions for seasonalization of tourist products are directly related to the diversification of tourist services. In other words, by diversifying the composition of tourist products, it is possible to maintain the amount of profit that can be lost due to the inconvenience caused by seasonality or to reduce the amount of expected damage. Therefore, one of the most important strategies related to seasonality is the diversification of tourism products and services. Since the objective need to diversify tourism services mainly consists of fluctuating trends of seasonality, it arises from the objective demand for rational and efficient use of this factor. The seasonality of tourism is often uncontrollable, its impact increases in parallel with the growth of tourism, on the other hand, seasonality also creates a loss of value called “seasonal loss”. If tourism services

are not adequately diversified, then the impact of seasonal business operations will lead to an uneven distribution of tourism resource use over time, as well as inefficient use of resources, loss of potential benefits, pressure on social and environmental opportunities, and systemic difficulties in administrative management.

2. The author's definition of the concept of seasonalization of tourist products has been developed. "Seasonality" means a recurring trend, i.e. a stable regularity, which is manifested in the annual increase or decrease of the level of one or another indicator for several years, reflecting the annual dynamics of one or another event. Therefore, in the modern interpretation, seasonality is explained in the form of dynamic fluctuating processes that determine the periods of growth and decline of various types of economic events and processes. Seasonality in the tourism industry is a process that is characteristic of a certain place, associated with changes in recreational conditions, and is caused by the cyclical nature of tourism activity throughout the year, although it is not necessarily systematic.

It seems advisable to conduct a prospective analysis of multiplicative seasonality and an analysis of seasonality using an indicator of congestion in the number of rooms.. Comparison of the results with the study will contribute to a deeper analysis of the studied object.

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